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Abstract: Deliverable D6.8 is a report on the open call implementation, the allocated resources distribution, and the outcomes of the accepted projects.

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List of Acronyms

ACE2	Angiotensin-Converting Enzyme 2
ACEMD	Accelerated Molecular Dynamics
API	Application Programming Interface
CCN	Cloud Condensation Nuclei
CERN	Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire
CoV-2	Coronavirus 2 variant Omicron
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DAFNE	Digital Anastylosis of Frescos challeNgE
DFT	Density Functional Theory
DFTB	Density Functional Tight Binding
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GATK	Genome Analysis Toolkit
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HEOM	Hierarchical Equations Of Motion
HPC	High-Performance Computing
IR	Infrared
IRMPD	Infrared Multiple Photon Dissociation
MC	Magnetic Clusters
MD	Molecular Dynamics
MPI	Message Passing Interface
NCC	Normalized Cross-Correlation
NGS	Next Generation Sequencing
NPF	New Particle Formation
OCR	Optical Character Recognition
OS	Operating System
PI	Principal Investigator
PID	Persistent Identifiers
QCD	Quantum Chromodynamics
QMC	Quantum Monte Carlo
RAS	Rat sarcoma
RBD	Receptor-Binding Domain
SARS	Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome

SCC	Self-Consistent Charge
SIMD	Single Instruction on Multiple Data
SMM	Single-Molecule Magnet
VM	Virtual Machine
WGS	Whole Genome Sequencing

Executive summary

What is the focus of this Deliverable?

The focus of this deliverable is to provide a report on the implementation of the pan-European open call of the NI4OS-Europe project [1] for proposals for projects using resources and services provided via the NI4OS-Europe catalogue [2]. We give the overview of the process and the objectives of the call, details of the allocated resource distribution, and the accepted projects' main outcomes.

What is next in the process to deliver the NI4OS-Europe results?

The specification of the open call, details of the process and the objectives of the call, and the available on-boarded EOSC services offered through the call were described in the Deliverable D6.5 - Open call specification. This deliverable is focused on the outcomes of the open call and the accepted projects' achievements. This is the final deliverable of WP6, due at the end of the project (February 2023). The allocation end date of awarded computational services was January 2023, while the data-oriented services will be available to the accepted open call projects until the March 2023.

What are the deliverable contents?

The Deliverable D6.8 - Report on the open call provides a description of the open call's implementation, the allocated resources distribution, and the accepted projects' outcomes. The description starts with a short introduction of the basic principles of the call. Next, the procedures, objectives, and details of the review process are given in Section 2. Section 3 lists all offered generic and thematic resources and repositories, as well as the distribution of the accepted projects over available resources. Implementation details and main outcomes of each accepted project are presented in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 provides the conclusions of the deliverable.

Conclusions and recommendations

During the NI4OS-Europe open call implementation, research teams of the accepted projects practically tested the complex EOSC environment hidden behind the resource catalogue, verifying seamlessness of the access, FAIR management, and reliable reusability of research data. To ensure the production of scientific results in the stipulated time, we allocated 6.2 million CPU-core hours, 402,000 GPU-card hours, 10,000 Xeon Phi-card hours, 364 VM cores, and a significant amount of storage space.

We have received 21 proposals, which underwent a technical and scientific review to determine the eligibility and suitability of applications for the requested services. In total, 20 projects were granted access to the NI4OS-Europe services: 5 Life Sciences, 2 Climatology, 4 Digital Cultural Heritage, 8 Computational Physics projects, and one project from the edge computing research field. These projects were granted 3.17 million CPU-core hours, 115,000 GPU-card hours, 166 VM cores, and 49 TBs of storage space.

From July 2022 to January 2023, the projects received full technical support via the project helpdesk, and as a result, 16 out of 20 projects were successfully finalized during the allocation period, while four didn't use or only partially use the allocated resources. All projects were presented during the EOSC Regional Event in Budapest, 5 of them had already published articles in peer-reviewed journals, while the others are working on the manuscripts.

1. Introduction

This deliverable describes the implementation of the pan-European open call for proposals for projects using services registered via the NI4OS-Europe catalogue [2] - one of the first catalogues integrated with the EOSC marketplace. Services registered within the NI4OS-Europe catalogue are categorized into repositories and thematic and generic services. The repositories bring together large sets of literature and data collections. Generic services provide generic capabilities and address technical needs common to multiple research areas, while thematic services are research community-specific services that provide value to the corresponding research groups. Throughout the call, the project offered all these resources to pan-European research communities, so that they can assess the scientific quality of these services, as well as to enable carrying out their research work.

The specification of the open call is described in the Deliverable D6.5 - Open call specification [3], which states the principles based on which the call is implemented:

- To make services and resources provided by the NI4OS-Europe service catalogue available to as many as possible researchers from the European region, as well as the Associate Countries, ensuring open, FAIR and unbiased access to those services;
- To promote the usage of the underlying generic services provided by the NI4OS-Europe resource provider partners to the whole European region;
- To promote scientific collaboration and exchange of know-how between the research groups following FAIR principles;
- To open the new knowledge and data created in the region to all researchers in Europe and beyond, where possible and where the interest is expressed;
- To provide the opportunity to researchers of all countries to have access to the EOSC on-boarded services offered by NI4OS-Europe.

Therefore, during the call execution, we insisted on data management harmonization according to the FAIR principles and practical open science implementation.

Section 2 of the deliverable summarizes the procedure, the objectives of the call, and a description of the review process. Section 3 provides all the information on the offered computational and storage resources, services, and the distribution of the accepted projects over available resources. Section 4 gives implementation details and the main outcomes of the project from the NI4OS-Europe open call. Although NI4OS-Europe has a highly interdisciplinary and cross-disciplinary character, it emphasizes the importance of services in the four flagship scientific fields of Life Sciences, Climate Sciences, Digital Cultural Science, and Computational Physics, which can provide timely solutions to problems relevant to the region. Therefore, the main outcomes of the open call projects are grouped into scientific domain subsections. Finally, Section 5 provides the conclusions of the deliverable.

2. Procedures, objectives, and the review process

The Deliverable D6.5 - Open call specification [3] details the process and the objectives of the call. In this section, we will briefly describe procedures and objectives and give more information on the review process.

The NI4OS-Europe open call was addressed to scientists and researchers that work in academic and research institutions in EU Member States and Associated Countries. We expected that 80% of the received proposals would address open research topics in specific fields of Life Sciences, Climate research, Digital Cultural Heritage, and Computational Physics and 20% in other scientific fields. Access to underlying computational resources (generic) was awarded for a maximum period of 6 months, while access to underlying storage resources was provided for up to 8 months.

For each flagship scientific field, we listed specific scientific and societal challenges to be addressed in the call, as well as the criteria for the evaluation of the projects during the review process:

- Scientific excellence;
- Scientific and/or social impact of the proposed research;
- The need for usage of the selected services and resources;
- The ability to provide project results (mainly data sets, but also services and software) as services for other researchers;
- Maturity and experience of the principal investigator and his/her team in the research field, as well as in using the selected resources and services;
- Feasibility of the project based on the technical evaluation and the availability of resources;
- Potential for collaboration among scientists in more than one eligible country for this call;
- Relevance with the above-mentioned scientific communities will be considered an asset;
- Gender balance.

All proposals were submitted electronically via the NI4OS-Europe survey tool. The application form was also available in a PDF format in order for applicants to have the full list of questions available. During the call, we provided support to applicants. Namely, NI4OS-Europe Access Team was available to answer questions while the call was open.

After the call's deadline, the organizing committee validated the applications, and where any clarifications were needed, they were asked to be provided by the 27th of May 2022. All proposals underwent a technical and scientific review to determine the eligibility and suitability of applications for the requested services and systems. Applications requesting large amounts of HPC/Cloud/Storage resources were also peer-reviewed by independent scientific experts from the region, taking into account conflict of interest and fairness issues. Reviewers were allowed to ask applicants for clarifications. Applications not requiring HPC/Cloud/Storage resources underwent a more lightweight review from scientific community leaders or other scientists. All reviews have been based on the criteria set in the "Scope and criteria of access" of the call.

The NI4OS-Europe access committee comprising of the NI4OS-Europe project technical board, prioritized the applications based on the criteria set in the "Scope and criteria of

access" of the call. The applicants were notified of the final results of the evaluation. In addition, successful applicants received further details regarding the allocated services and resources and the process of obtaining user accounts.

3. Resources offered through the call

Detailed list of the offered resources to the open call for proposals for projects using resources and services provided via the NI4OS-Europe catalogue is given in the Deliverable D6.5 - Open call specification [3]. Practically all resources registered within the catalogue are offered during the call. Access mode of some of these resources is free or free-conditionally, typically for repositories and thematic services. On the other hand, the others have peer-reviewed or excellence-based access modes, typical for computing-intensive thematic services and infrastructure services, such as HPC clusters and Cloud sites. Therefore, it was important to allocate computing resources that would be offered in the call and used by the accepted projects.

Resource allocation is done in collaboration with the resource providers. In this process, we allocated 6.2 million CPU-core hours, 402,000 GPU-card hours, and 10,000 Xeon Phi-card hours at ARIS, Avitohol, Isabella, PARADOX, Cyclone, and Leo HPC installations. The Data analysis service, which is a Hadoop-based cluster, allocated 200,000 CPU hours for the open call projects. In total, 364 VM cores were allocated at FINKI, ICIPRO, Avitohol, GCloud.ge, and ASNET-AM Cloud sites. Although the working storage space is by default provided together with computational and Cloud resources, additional storage for archiving purposes was allocated at the Archival service (10 TB per project) and for sharing purposes at the Simple storage service (100 GB per user account).

Although a majority of thematic services and repositories offered through the call are free, within the call we emphasized that all accepted projects will be granted dedicated support via the project's helpdesk during the call. Furthermore, repositories registered in the catalogue commonly contain institutional publications and data, and could be used in read-only mode. Therefore, the NI4OS-Europe general-purpose repository is offered for publishing purposes. This repository holds regional community datasets, but it is also the platform to host all kinds of additional data, such as publications (and their associated data), software (or references to software), workflow descriptions (e.g., how to generate research data), or even materials targeting the general public (e.g., images, videos, etc.).

Since the HPC clusters and Cloud sites have excellence-based access modes, we organized a technical and scientific review to determine the eligibility and suitability of applications for the requested services. After the review process, we ended up with 20 project proposals. All accepted projects requested at least one type of generic services. In total 16 projects, out of 20, requested computational time, five projects requested VMs at Cloud infrastructure, and two asked for storage at the Archival service. In addition, six projects requested access to thematic services and three asked access to the NI4OS-Europe repository service.

Based on the technical requirements of the proposals, we distributed these requests over previously allocated resources. Table 1 summarizes this distribution. For each project, it gives a total amount of offered CPU-core hours, GPU-card hours, and storage space at one of the regional HPC clusters. The amount of offered CPU-core hours varies from 10,000 to 1,000,000, and GPU-card hours from 5,000 to 50,000. Due to high demands for NVIDIA V100 Tensor Core GPU by several proposals, the offered GPU-card time (30,000 GPU-card hours) for the KRAS_adaptive application was distributed on the ARIS and Cyclone HPC site. In total, we offered 3.17 million CPU-core hours, 115,000 GPU-card hours, and 49 TBs of storage space to all projects accepted in the open call.

Project acronym	HPC cluster	CPU-core hours	GPU-card hours	Storage (TB)
EPICENTER	PARADOX	100,000	-	6
ERE-GWAS	Isabella	250,000	-	10
KRAS_adaptive	ARIS/Cyclone	-	30,000	2
CLOUD	Cyclone	500,000	10,000	8
RS3L	Leo HPC	-	5,000	10
PRD	Leo HPC	50,000	50,000	1
RINCCAS-HPC	Avitohol	250,000	-	-
AVISPEED	Leo HPC	10,000	5,000	1
TAVS-TAG	Avitohol	50,000	-	2
DFTB-GPR	Avitohol	50,000	-	2
MAGNANO	Avitohol	500,000	-	1
FL4GLUE	Isabella	100,000	-	1
CoNTraSt	ARIS	300,000	-	1
ChFITrHM	ARIS	1,000,000	-	1
PLAIN	ARIS	10,000	10,000	1
NFLGT	Leo HPC	-	10,000	2
		3,170,000	115,000	49

Table 1: Selected applications and awarded computational services in the open call

Table 2 lists projects that requested access to the Cloud infrastructure and the amount of granted resources. The number of requested virtual machines varies from 2 to 6, while the amount of requested VM cores per such machine varies from 1 to 32. Therefore, we granted 19 virtual machines with 166 VM cores in total. These resources are used in different ways by the accepted projects. For example, some of them used VMs with public IP numbers to deploy thematic services or backup/fail-over instances of the services. On the other hand, the SANDPAPER used the offered Cloud resources for research purposes. In particular, that project analyzed and optimized the performances of edge resource migration in a highly dynamic environment with frequently changing user requirements.

Project acronym	Cloud site	Virtual machines	Virtual machine-cores
ACPSDTDDS	FINKI	4	16
PRD	GCloud.ge	5	10
TAVS-TAG	FINKI	2	16
DFTB-GPR	FINKI	2	64
SANDPAPER	ICIPRO	6	60
		19	166

Table 2: Selected applications and awarded Cloud resources in the open call

The list of offered thematic services and repositories is given in Table 3. As it was expected, the digital cultural heritage project PRD was interested to use thematic services from its areas, such as CHERE and Digital Library. Also, computational physics projects (TAVS-TAG, DFTB-GPR, MAGNANO) requested thematic services such as Gaussian API for fitting repulsive potentials in density-functional tight-binding with Gaussian process regression or Schrödinger API for solving multidimensional time-independent Schrödinger equation. PRD, MAGNANO, and FL4GLUE projects requested the NI4OS-Europe repository for dataset upload.

Project acronym	Thematic services and repositories
PRD	CHERE, Digital Library, NI4OS-Europe repository, LCT
Smaryd	OMApp
TAVS-TAG	Schrödinger API
DFTB-GPR	Gaussian API
MAGNANO	Gaussian API, Schrödinger API, OMApp, NI4OS-Europe repository
FL4GLUE	NI4OS-Europe repository

Table 3: Selected applications and awarded thematic services and repositories in the open call

SPIKE-COVID19 and PRD projects requested access to the Archival service and were granted 10 TB and 3 TB of storage space, respectively. In both cases, the archival service is used to store a large number of produced datasets. In the case of the SPIKE-COVID19 project, the ARIS team that hosts archival service allowed the project team to transfer their data physically using hard drives.

4. Open call projects

In this section, we present implementation details and the main outcomes of the projects accepted in the NI4OS-Europe open call. In Table 4 we list acronyms and full titles of the accepted projects. 16 out of 20 projects were successfully finalized, while four did not use or only partially used the allocated resources. The reasons for this are different. In the case of the ERE-GWAS project, although the team started using resources, one of the team's key members left the institute, so the project had to be canceled. The PI of the AVISPEED project did not successfully set up the necessary software libraries within the planned time, while the Smarty and NFLGT project teams decided not to use the provided resources.

Projects are grouped into scientific domain subsections: Life Science, Climate Research, Digital Cultural Heritage, Computational Physics, and Others. For each project a brief background and the aim of the project are given. We described the project teams' experience during the service access provision and eventual technical issues identified, as well as implementations and outcomes, together with problems faced during this process. Also, we collected the feedback on how the current procedure could be more efficient in supporting and reaching future potential users. All related publications that are made or are in preparation are listed in this section. The future plans for each project are reported as well.

	Project acronym	Project name
Life sciences	EPICENTER	Employing High Performance Computing System for Building up a Germline Variant Calling Pipeline for Human Whole Genome Data
	ERE-GWAS	Genome-wide association study of Epizootic rabbit enteropathy tolerance
	KRAS_adaptive	Exploring the free energy landscape of K-Ras4B dimers with Raf effectors on a model membrane using adaptive MD simulations
	SPIKE-COVID19	Assessment of mutations on RBD in the Spike protein of SARS-CoV-2 WT, Alpha, Delta, B1.1.318, and Omicron variants
	ACPSDTDDS	A Cloud Platform for Simulations and Discovery of Targeted Drug Delivery Systems
Climate research	CLOUD	Monsoon Upper Atmosphere New Particle Formation
	RS3L	Remote sensing self supervised learning

Digital cultural heritage	PRD	Platform for Document Revitalization
	RINCCAS-HPC	Rotation-Invariant Normalized Cross-Correlation method for 2D color matching of Arbitrary Shaped fragments of a fresco in a HPC resources environment
	AVISPEED	Audio-video-based vehicle detection and speed estimation
	Smardy	Marketplace for technology transfer of R&I data, software and results
Computational physics	TAVS-TAG	Theoretical anharmonic vibrational spectroscopy of protonated betaine and glycine tagged with molecular hydrogen
	DFTB-GPR	DFTB repulsive potentials in molecular solids from Gaussian Process Regression
	MAGNANO	Study of magnetic nanoclusters with d-f metals
	FL4GLUE	The glueball spectrum with four light dynamical quarks
	CoNTraSt	Coherent Nanoscale Transport in Strongly Interacting Electron-Phonon Systems
	ChFITrHM	Charge Fluctuations and Transport in the Hubbard model
	PLAIN	Probing Lattice gauge theories using Artificial Intelligent Networks
	NFLGT	Normalizing flows for lattice gauge theories
Other	SANDPAPER	Simulating ANd DePloying an Adaptive and Proactive Edge fRamework

Table 4: List of the accepted open call projects

4.1. Life sciences projects

This section reports Life Sciences projects granted access to NI4OS-Europe resources in the open call. Table 5 lists all these projects, principal investigators, and their countries. Unfortunately, the ERE-GWAS project report is missing since one of the team's key members left the institute soon after the projects started.

Project acronym	Principal investigator	Principal investigator country
EPICENTER	Biljana Stankovic	Serbia
ERE-GWAS	Levente Kontra	Hungary
KRAS_adaptive	Zoe Cournia	Greece
SPIKE-COVID19	Zoe Cournia	Greece
ACPSDTDDS	Elena Kusevska	North Macedonia

Table 5: List of accepted Life sciences projects, corresponding principal investigators and their countries

4.1.1. EPICENTER

Next generation sequencing (NGS) enabled the production of hundreds of giga base pair information per one sample of whole genomic data in the form of scattered sequence reads. In order to interpret these data, a bioinformatics analysis entails a multistep process that uses different software to line up the reads with the reference genome and looks for variations in the genetic code that could be disease causing, having a modifying effect on phenotypic traits or influence person's response to therapy. The analysis of these large data sets requires more storage and computing power than most conventional computers can provide, making high-performance computers (HPC) a preferred choice for whole genome sequencing (WGS) data analysis.

The EPICENTER project team was working on the construction of a Germline Variant Calling Pipeline for processing human whole genome data sets produced by the MGI DNBSEQ technology. The PARADOX HPC system at the Institute of Physics Belgrade has been used for WGS analysis software testing and optimization. Through the open call of the NI4OS-Europe project, the EPICENTER team was awarded 100,000 CPU hours and 6 TBs of storage space. During the pipeline development, the team installed different open-source bioinformatics tools on PARADOX and transferred in-house made FASTQ files of the standard human genome (NA12878), which is used for testing and optimization of these tools.

To analyze WGS data, the EPICENTER team performed adapter clipping and quality filtering of raw reads using the fastp tool, and proceeded to read mapping using different tools such as bwa and bwa-mem2. After filtering and indexing reads using samtools they

performed marking duplicates and recalibration using Picard, sambamba and Doppelmark tools. Finally, they tested two variant calling tools freebayes and GATK's HaplotypeCaller.

At this point of testing, the team was able to decide on almost all open-source tools they were going to incorporate into the pipeline. However, the EPICENTER project team still needs to test a few variant callers and different parameters for chosen tools and write proper scripts. Nevertheless, the PARADOX HPC system tremendously reduced the time and cost of software testing and development of the WGS pipeline. To exemplify, here we report in Table 6 the comparison of different tools used for marking duplicates of the same 116 GB file in terms of computational resources.

Markduplicates tool	Real time (h)	Number of threads (average)	CPU hours	Memory usage peak (GB)
Picard	17.2	77	1299	233
Sambamba	1.6	20	30.5	10
Doppelmark	0.5	21	10.5	71

Table 6: Comparing performance and resource usage of different tools used for marking duplicates

By January 2023, the EPICENTER team finalized work on the pipeline construction. The pipeline is also benchmarked. Future steps will involve publishing a developed pipeline in an internationally recognized journal. Also, the team plans to make the pipeline open-source and available to the scientific community.

The final version of the pipeline will primarily be used for processing human whole genome data sets produced using the MGI DNBSEQ technology at the Center for genome sequencing and bioinformatics at the Institute of Molecular Genetics and Genetic Engineering (IMGGE). Until now, the team has sequenced more than sixty genomes of patients with rare diseases and patients with multifactorial diseases in which we will search for new genetic modifiers and new pharmacogenomics markers. The developed pipeline will be available for future research, in particular, two ongoing IMGGE lead projects will involve WGS analysis of 1,250 individuals from the Western Balkan region using the MGI DNBSEQ technology, which will rely on this pipeline for bioinformatics analysis.

4.1.2. KRAS_adaptive

KRAS_adaptive project aims to characterize the dimerization free energy landscape of the oncogene KRas-4B in its wild-type as well as in its oncogenic G12D mutant form in the presence and absence of its effector protein on a model cell membrane. This study could lead to the identification of key conformations and kinetics of the K-Ras4B dimer that hold biologically critical information, which can be further exploited in the discovery of novel therapeutics.

K-Ras4B is the most frequently mutated isoform in human cancers (83% of RAS mutations). Approximately one-third of all human cancers harbor an oncogenic mutation in at least one RAS gene, rendering Ras proteins the most commonly mutated oncoproteins. Among them, K-Ras4B is the most frequently mutated isoform in human cancers (83% of all RAS mutations), while in some pancreatic adenocarcinomas, it is

mutated in nearly 90% of tumors. Specifically, it has been proposed that when K-Ras4B dimerizes on the membrane, Raf uses K-Ras4B as a scaffold to anchor and form dimers on its own, which are essential for Raf activation leading to cell proliferation. Dimerization is critical for the activity of wild-type (WT) K-Ras4B, as well as for the oncogenic ability of mutant G12D K-Ras4B according to a study that showed that K-Ras4B dimerization is essential for activation of downstream signaling and cell growth *in vitro* and *in vivo*, and also suggested a role for disruption of dimerization as a therapeutic strategy for K-Ras4B mutant cancers. However, the mechanism with which Ras proteins dimerize on the membrane and a conclusive, biologically-relevant K-Ras4B dimer structure has not been yet established. This project aims to combine a) adaptive sampling molecular dynamics (MD) simulations with Markov State Modeling and b) Coarse-Grained Metadynamics Molecular Dynamics simulations to describe the free energy landscape and kinetics of the dimerization of one of the most common mutants of K-Ras4B, G12D, in the presence and the absence of Raf effectors on a model membrane.

KRAS_adaptive project was granted 30,000 GPU V100 card hours (15,000 at Cyclone HPC center and 15,000 card hours at ARIS HPC center). The team asked for additional time, and this request was approved, so in total, 42,000 GPU card hours were consumed by the project.

The team ran adaptive MD simulations of the K-Ras4B dimer system in the presence and absence of Raf effectors on a membrane for the following systems: WT K-Ras4B dimer without Raf effectors on a model membrane and WT Ras4B dimer with Raf effectors on a model membrane, starting from two different experimentally derived structures (PDB ID: 5VQ2 and PDB ID: 6W4E) using the software ACEMD3 for MD simulations together with HTMD for Markov state modeling. They achieved 25.6 μ s for each system (total > 100 μ s). Figure 1 shows an example of the reweighted free energy surface for the K-Ras4B dimer without an effectors system (PDB ID: 6W4E). However, even at the 25 μ s timescale, the simulations did not explore the full free energy landscape of K-Ras4B dimer, possibly due to limited sampling.

KRAS_adaptive team, therefore, also used Coarse-Grained molecular dynamics (MD) simulations with enhanced sampling techniques (PT-METAD-WTE) and the Martini 3 force field, which led to a significant speed-up of the simulations. They used GROMACS (v. 2021.5) patched with PLUMED (v. 2.8.0), with MPI and GPU support. At the coarse-grained representation, the systems explored the full free energy dimerization landscape. Figure 2 shows a comparison of the free energy landscape of the wild-type (A) and G12D mutant (B) systems.

As of January 2023, all simulations have concluded, and the project team is in the process of finalizing the data analysis and preparing a manuscript for submission in the first quarter of 2023.

During the use of allocated resources, the project team was faced with several technical issues that occurred while using the resources. These problems were successfully tackled very fast with the help of Cyclone and ARIS HPC system administrators. The resources were provided within a reasonable time (approximately two months since the participation decision), and no problems occurred during this process.

Figure 1: The reweighted free energy surface for the 6W4E without effectors system projected in the first two TICA components. For each macrostate, the extracted minima structure is shown. The different K-Ras4B monomers are depicted with blue and red, and the $\alpha 4/\alpha 5$ helices with yellow. The position of the first frame of the NMR structure of PDB ID 6W4E is marked with a red cross. The RMSD between PDB ID 6W4E and the extracted structures are shown above each structure. The membrane plane is depicted with a black dotted line

Figure 2: Dimerization free energy landscape of KRas-4B with RAF effector (RBD + CRD). Panel A corresponds to the wild-type and panel B to the G12D mutant system, respectively. The X axis shows the RMSD from the starting structure of the simulation (PDBid: 5vq2) and the Y axis the distance between the geometric center of the two KRas-4B monomers (excluding the flexible HVR). Cyan crosses indicate positions of energy minima of the landscape. The color of the landscape indicates energy values, with deeper shades corresponding to deeper minima

4.1.3. SPIKE-COVID19

The severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) coronavirus 2 (CoV-2) variant Omicron spread more rapidly than other variants of the SARS-CoV-2 virus. Mutations on the Spike (S) protein receptor-binding domain (RBD) and N terminal domain are critical for antibody resistance and infectivity of the SARS-CoV-2 variants. Antibody development efforts mainly revolve around the extensively glycosylated SARS-CoV-2 spike (S) protein, which mediates the host cell entry by binding to the angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2). Similar to many other viruses, the SARS-CoV-2 spike utilizes a glycan shield to thwart the host's immune response. Here, we built and simulated full-length models of glycosylated SARS-CoV-2 S protein, both in the open and closed states, in the WT, alpha, delta, omicron BA1 and B.1.1.318 variants. Multiple microsecond-long, all-atom Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations were used to provide an atomistic perspective on the roles of glycans, and the protein structure and dynamics. This rich dataset of 3TB provides critical functional and structural information into the SARS-CoV-2 S protein and its glycan coat in the most recognized protein variants. The aim of this study is to exploit this information to provide insight regarding the role of the mutations of the variants of concern in virus transmissibility, host immunity (due to past infection or vaccination) evasion as well as in the design of novel antibodies effective against novel emerging variants (Figure 3). Finally, the SPIKE-COVID19 project team would like to make this dataset available for analysis by the broader scientific community that may be useful in small molecule, antibody or vaccine development.

Figure 3: Illustration of the aim of the project. Spike, colored in green, is embedded in a model membrane and contains glycans, colored in red, and mutations colored in magenta

Over the past two years, the world has been ravaged by a global pandemic caused by the novel coronavirus SARS-CoV-2. Also fueled by the tens of millions of people infected, this new coronavirus is characterized by a high rate of mutagenesis, which has led to several novel variants with global or local prevalence. Although extensive studies have not been performed for many of those strains, it is believed that fast-spreading mutations might affect virus infectivity, replication and/or immunogenicity. The Greek Genome Center of the Biomedical Research Foundation of the Academy of Athens (BRFAA) is the leading Institute within the National Genomic Surveillance Network for SARS-CoV-2 variants. The

National Genomic surveillance effort was initiated on January 19, 2021, and since then and BRFAA has completed the genomic characterization of more than 10,000 randomly selected samples from all Greek regions. Genomic analysis has revealed 5,238 cases assigned as 20I/501Y.V1/B.1.1.7 (VOC_202012/01 first detected in the UK), 29 cases assigned as 20H/501Y.V2/B.1.351(VOC_202012/02 first detected in South Africa), and 419 cases assigned as 20B/B.1.1.318 of unknown origin, that has been designated as VUI_202102/04 since March 4, 2021, from Public Health England. Moreover, other variants such as alpha, delta, and, more lately, omicron BA1 have emerged. Genotypic analysis of B.1.1.318 variant in the Greek population, showed that this strain contains missense mutations in genes encoding for the Spike, N, M, and NSP proteins. Mutations in the S gene are single nucleotide substitutions or in frame deletions resulting in: (1) p.D796H, (2) p.T95I, (3) pY144del, (4) p.P681H, (5) p.D614G and (6) p.E484K.

Here, have performed multiple microsecond simulations long MD studies of the mutated spike proteins in the B.1.1.318 variant, omicron, delta, alpha, and the WT for comparison in the presence of the glycan shield and a model cell membrane and in the open and closed conformations. The substantial increase in the number and proportion of B.1.1.318 variant cases in the Athens area is highly concerning in terms of transmissibility or the ability to evade the host immune response. Furthermore, it is unknown whether this variant has a selective advantage over B.1.1.7 that currently predominates in the area, and thereby has the potential to compete in the Athens area where the two variants co-circulate. Within this context and under the pressure of the emergence of new variants of concern, the aim of this study is to provide insight regarding the role of these mutations in virus transmissibility, host immunity (due to past infection or vaccination) evasion as well as in the design of novel antibodies effective against novel emerging variants. The dataset will be made fully available and accessible to the scientific community.

The Archival service of the ARIS HPC system has provided access to the SPIKE-COVID19 project team within a reasonable time. Also, the ARIS team allowed the project team to transfer their data using hard drives. SPIKE-COVID19 project team experience during the service access provision was pleasant as ARIS' staff was helpful, easy to reach, and able to answer all questions. In addition, SPIKE-COVID19 team has already produced a rich dataset of the full-length glycosylated SARS-CoV-2 S protein, both in the open and closed states, in the WT, alpha, delta, omicron BA1 and B1.1.318 variants in the presence of a model cell membrane. Specifically, they have performed 800 ns-long, all-atom MD simulations that were used to provide an atomistic perspective on the roles of glycans, and the protein structure and dynamics, which produced 3TB. The produced dataset has been saved in hard drives, and thus the only pending issue was to transfer the data to the archival service of ARIS's Archival service.

SPIKE-COVID19 project team plan to analyze the produced dataset to provide insight regarding the role of the mutations of the variants of concern in virus transmissibility, host immunity (due to past infection or vaccination) evasion, as well as in the design of novel antibodies effective against novel emerging variants. The results will be published in a paper that will also point to the PID of the dataset so that it can be widely shared with the scientific community.

The provided amount of storage space at the Archival service was adequate for the purpose of computational chemistry projects. In addition, the storage services are easily

accessible, and the support from the ARIS staff is of high caliber, so no further actions were required regarding the service provisioning access.

4.1.4. ACPSDTDDS

The main goal of the proposed research project was to identify the major challenges in utilizing cloud resources for the computational study of targeted drug delivery systems. Computational approaches for the study of targeted drug delivery systems employ physical models with scales ranging from atomic to macroscopic. Their implementations rely heavily on parallel programming and efficient use of high-performance computing resources. However, due to their wide applicability, these methods are also attractive to smaller companies and research and educational institutions that may not have access to enough or any on-premise high-performance computing resources. Cloud computing, with its pay-per-use model and the elasticity of provisioning cloud resources, can be a good alternative for such users. Additionally, cloud resources also find use in large hybrid distributed architectures to supplement available resources during times of higher loads.

It is, however, challenging to achieve performance comparable to traditional high-performance computing architectures on the cloud. As a consequence of virtualization and lower network speeds, cloud resources perform more poorly for algorithms where more inter-processor communication is required.

The Multiple-Instruction-Multiple-Data parallelism used in scientific computing applications is achieved by utilizing shared memory and distributed memory architectures. Both architectures can be simulated in a cloud environment. We can simulate a shared memory architecture by adding multiple cores on a virtual machine and a distributed memory architecture by setting up multiple instances and configuring them with the Message Passing Interface (MPI) standard. We can study the performance and scaling of different algorithms commonly used in computational chemistry on cloud resources for both architectures by varying the number of instances and the number of cores on each instance.

In order to produce such setups, a small number of resources on the FINKI cloud have been made available for this project. Access to the FINKI cloud resources was provided immediately upon the start of the project. The service has been stable throughout. FINKI cloud is deployed through OpenStack, a well-known and well-documented set of open-source software components for cloud infrastructure. NOVA is used for computing services, and NEUTRON for networking.

For the ACPSDTDDS project, we have allocated 10 CPU cores, 10 data storage volumes, 16 GB RAM, and 10 virtual machines. With this setup, the ACPSDTDDS team was able to vary the distribution of resources from one to ten single-core instances and from one to five multi-core instances. This allowed them to study the scaling of both distributed memory and shared memory approaches, as well as hybrid approaches. In particular, they identified the limit of speedup due to overhead as a function of network speed. The MPI cluster has been set up, and a standard procedure for this, with different VM configurations, is defined. Currently, the team is in the process of selecting and implementing the algorithms. Once the initial tests are completed, designing an optimal database for storing, accessing, and searching the data will also be necessary. This will provide a gateway to defining the basic guidelines for implementing the algorithms necessary for solving targeted drugs.

4.2. Climate research projects

We have received two proposals from the climate research field in the open call. Table 7 lists all these projects, principal investigators, and their countries. Both projects were successfully finalized during the resource allocation period, and the CLOUD project team already published a paper in an international, peer-reviewed, open access journal.

Project acronym	Principal investigator	Principal investigator country
CLOUD	Theo Christoudias	Cyprus
RS3L	Vladimir Risojevic	Bosnia and Herzegovina

Table 7: List of accepted Climate research projects, corresponding principal investigators and their countries

4.2.1. CLOUD

New particle formation (NPF) and growth in the atmosphere affect climate, weather, air quality, and human health. It is the first step of the complex process leading to cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) formation. Even though there is a wealth of observations from field measurements (in forests, high-altitude, polar regions, coastal and urban sites, and aircraft campaigns), as well as laboratory studies of multi-component nucleation (including the CLOUD chamber at CERN), the NPF parameterizations in global models are lacking. These deficiencies, in large part, make the impacts of aerosols one of the highest sources of uncertainty in global climate change modeling and associated impacts on weather and human health. The CLOUD project couples the latest observations and model developments in the EMAC global climate-chemistry model to capture feedback, quantify impacts, and reduce uncertainties in the contemporary challenges of air quality and climate change, in partnership with the CLOUD Collaboration and the Max Planck Institute for Chemistry (MPIC).

Modeling atmospheric composition and climate change on a global scale remain a great scientific challenge. Earth system models spend up to 85% of their total required computational resources on the integration of atmospheric chemical kinetics due to the stiffness of the system caused by the widely different lifetimes of participating species. In addition, such simulations require high energy demands, a great amount of memory, and engage a great probability of hardware failure. On the other hand, memory optimization that comes when using single-precision will allow the community to perform multi-decadal very-high-resolution simulations with coupled chemistry down to the convection-resolution limit.

For CLOUD project purposes, the NI4OS-Europe allocated 500,000 CPU-core and 10,000 GPU-card hours at the Cyclone HPC cluster provided by the Cyprus Institute. These resources are being exploited to run single- and multi-node atmospheric chemical kinetics simulations and extract performance metrics in terms of required runtime, speedup, and scalability. Figure 4 illustrates time-to-solution for EMAC model in QCTM configuration at T42L90 resolution: circulation dynamics ECHAM and physics MESSy (Cyan), and the total

required runtime in double precision (red). The red hatched area indicates the improvement in runtime that can be achieved by the mixed-precision KPP compared to the double-precision KPP.

Through the open call, the CLOUD team managed to transform double precision chemical kinetics simulation to single precision in the KPP model and ran unit tests in a global climate-chemistry model. Following this, they demonstrated the stability of the simulations and achieved an accuracy within less than 1% of relative difference compared to double precision. With this, we have effectively halved the required simulation memory, and we are projecting better scalability on HPC systems. Additionally, the CLOUD project team explicitly exposed Single Instruction on Multiple Data (SIMD) vectorizations through the use of compiler intrinsics for all linear algebra operations of the simulation, which further accelerated the simulations by up to 30%.

Figure 4: Time-to-solution for EMAC model in QCTM configuration at T42L90 resolution: circulation dynamics ECHAM and physics MESSy (Cyan), and the total required runtime in double precision (red). The red hatched area indicates the improvement in runtime that can be achieved by the mixed-precision KPP compared to the double-precision KPP

The CLOUD project team employed a number of NI4OS-Europe generic services in different aspects of the data lifecycle, from creation to processing, analysis, preservation, access, and reuse. These include generic HPC computing, generic storage, model input data staging, and output preservation, and advanced in-situ data management, processing, and workflow management. As a result, the project team published a paper in the international, peer-reviewed, open access journal *Atmosphere*, which is titled, *Reduced-Precision Chemical Kinetics in Atmospheric Models* [4].

4.2.2. RS3L

Accurate land cover/land use data are essential for addressing global challenges such as urbanization and climate change. In the past decade, state-of-the-art deep learning techniques have emerged as a promising approach for automatic land cover/land use classification of remote sensing images. However, deep learning methods are extremely data-hungry, and the main obstacle to their widespread exploitation in remote sensing is the scarcity of labeled remote sensing image data that can be used for supervised training. Self-supervised learning is an approach with the potential to remove the heavy dependency on labeled training data in domains where large labeled datasets do not exist. In this project, the team aimed to investigate the transfer performance of self-supervised learning methods to target remote sensing image classification tasks.

A standard approach for applying deep learning in remote sensing image analysis has been to start with a deep learning model pre-trained on a large dataset containing labeled general-purpose images and either use it for feature extraction or fine-tune it to the target task. The most common dataset used for supervised pre-training is ImageNet, with 1.2 million images manually classified into 1,000 object categories. However, the distribution of remote sensing images is different from the distribution of the images in ImageNet, and recent research has shown that supervised pre-training on remote sensing datasets can match or even outperform supervised ImageNet pre-training for some remote sensing image analysis tasks. The transfer performance of supervised and self-supervised ImageNet models can be improved by additional supervised pre-training using remote sensing image data. Consequently, it would be interesting to investigate whether additional pre-training using remote sensing images improves the performance of self-supervised ImageNet models on target remote sensing tasks.

The RS3L project was awarded computing resources on Hungary's Leo cluster. Leo cluster nodes have NVIDIA K20x and K40x GPUs with compute capability 3.5. However, the code used by the RS3L project's team depends on the PyTorch library for deep learning, which does not support GPUs with compute capability 3.5. Therefore, they could not install and run an up-to-date version of PyTorch and use the existing codebase and, more importantly, pre-trained models. As a result, the team decided not to rewrite the code but rather to switch to using the ETFBL-CC01 cluster for further development and experiments. The access to the ETFBL-CC01 cluster was provided in time, the whole process was very streamlined, and there were no problems encountered during this process. During the project the team used 4,200 hours of GPU-card time on the ETFBL-CC01 computing infrastructure.

During the project, the team experimented with using self-supervised ImageNet models as a basis for training remote-sensing image classifiers. Their experimental results show that when self-supervised ImageNet models are used as fixed feature extractors, the performances of the classifiers trained on downstream remote sensing image classification tasks are comparable to the performances obtained when feature extractors are pre-trained on high-resolution remote sensing images. Furthermore, when the networks pre-trained using self-supervised techniques are end-to-end fine-tuned, the classification accuracies on remote sensing image classification tasks are consistently better than in the cases when supervised ImageNet, or in-domain pre-training is used. Finally, when a second round of supervised pre-training on remote sensing images is performed, the obtained results are further improved.

The fine-tuned models are used in web service and application for remote sensing scene classification available at <https://rs2c.etfbl.net/upload>. In addition, to the existing functionalities of multi-class and multi-label classification, the RS3L team also added patch-based image classification with or without smoothing. Screenshots of the web application with some examples of the results are shown in Figure 5.

RS3L experiments were limited to a second round of supervised pre-training using labeled remote-sensing images. However, it would be interesting to start with self-supervised models and perform the second round also in a self-supervised manner. This would further reduce the need for manually labeled training images. The RS3L team plans to pursue this direction in the future. Additionally, it would be interesting to explore the transferability of representations to other target tasks, such as object detection and semantic segmentation.

Figure 5: Screenshot of the RS2C web application showing the results of the patch-based land cover classification without (left) and with (right) result smoothing

4.3. Digital cultural heritage projects

In total, 4 Digital cultural heritage projects were granted access to the NI4OS-Europe services during the open call. Projects' acronyms, principal investigators, and their countries are given in Table. Unfortunately, only two of them, PRD and RINCCAS-HPC are successfully finalized. The AVISPEED project team did not successfully set up the necessary software libraries within the planned time, while the Smarty project team decided not to use the provided resources. The other two projects were more prosperous, and the RINCCAS-HPC project team already presented the project results at several conferences.

Project acronym	Principal investigator	Principal investigator country
PRD	Tudor Bumbu	Moldova
RINCCAS-HPC	Dimo Dimov	Bulgaria
AVISPEED	Slobodan Djukanovic	Montenegro

Smardy	Victor Suci	Romania
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Table 8: List of accepted Digital cultural heritage projects, corresponding principal investigators, and their countries

4.3.1. PRD

The aim of the PRD project was to develop tools (mainly trained OCR models) and resources for digitizing old Romanian documents printed in Cyrillic Script. The team applied for computational resources in order to accelerate OCR training and to try to make the training task crowdsourced. Libraries in Moldova and Romania have more than 850,000 pages to be digitized, so the need for OCR models is crucial in the process of digitization. Figure 6 illustrates the technological process of digitization of old Romanian printed texts and the use of HPC.

Figure 6: Overview of the technological process in the digitization of old Romanian documents. With red is marked the HPC need in this process

The project was granted 50,000 CPU-hours, 50,000 GPU-hours, 1TB Storage of Leo HPC and GCloud.ge cloud service. Additionally, 10TB of storage service ARIS archival was also allocated. The Leo HPC and GCloud.ge cloud service are being leveraged to train Optical Character Recognition (OCR) models. The use of HPC has allowed for the processing of large amounts of data in a relatively short period of time, making the training process highly efficient. The efficient training process was crucial in ensuring that the OCR models were trained with accuracy and efficiency. In total, 8 OCR models were trained. Current technical challenge for the PRD team is to create a web-based platform to enable training by multiple specialists. Therefore, the need for HPC is still crucial to the team.

The PRD deployed the platform for digitization, which is available at <https://digitizare.math.md/>. The team plans to present the results at the Workshop on Intelligent Information Systems 2023.

4.3.2. RINCCAS-HPC

The RINCCAS-HPC project team aims to deploy a service within an HPC environment. The service is based on the RINCCAS method [5] for the reconstruction of a color fresco from its ruins (Figure 7), i.e., a set of fragments of arbitrary shapes, often less or more damaged by time and possibly mixed with other, spurious ones. The RINCCAS method was originally developed at the ICT-BAS for participation in the DAFNE (Digital Anastylis of Frescos challeNgE) computer competition [6] organized in June-July 2019, and this is a well-known problem in world heritage conservation practice.

For reasons of higher precision, RINCCAS is based on the classical Normalized Cross-Correlation (NCC) method for image matching and has been extended for RGB color scheme, rotational invariance, and fragment shapes independence. The RINCCAS-HPC project team introduced MACIR-approximation of the fragment area, demonstrating a significant advantage of the RINCCAS method over the known similar methods. The first phase of the method is computationally intensive since the method complexity increases log-cubically with increasing the resolution of presented images. Still, the obtained precise positioning of the fragments allows stable identification of the spurious among them in the second phase of the method. The RINCCAS phase 2 is quite faster. It has a linear complexity relative to the number of fragments and/or their areas and can be used for interactive expert optimization in recognition of false fragments, which seems a very important quantity, especially for expert restorers.

Figure 7: Illustration of the main application of RINCCAS

The NI4OS-Europe allocated resources at the Bulgarian Avitohol HPC installation for this project. In total, 250,000 CPU-core hours have been provided, and the RINCCAS-HPC project team received practical support from the Avitohol team. In particular, the original RINCCAS software has been significantly optimized for efficient HPC performance. A series of incremental software improvements have been implemented and tested in the HPC environment. The team found the optimal loading schedule of the provided resource, which is 32 cores on a cluster anode (a specific case of the "knapsack problem"). Although achieved scaling is acceptable, the team is planning to furtherly improve the performance of the parallel version of the code. For example, the duration of a RINCCAS-HPC experiment is approximately inversely proportional to the number of cores used but generally remains "logarithmic cubic". Alternative approaches include the calculation of the NCC map faster, e.g., via content based image retrieval or convolutional neural network. Also, the team is interested in deploying a web-based service that will provide more user-friendly access to the RINCCAS-HPC outputs.

The RINCCAS-HPC project team presented the results of the project at the Regional conference organized by the NI4OS-Europe project [7], the EuroCC conference High-

performance computing for the benefit of researchers and society [8], and at the 17th Annual Meeting of the Bulgarian Section of SIAM [9].

4.4. Computational physics projects

Table 9 lists the Computational physics projects, principal investigators, and their countries. We have accepted eight projects from North Macedonia, Moldova, Cyprus, Serbia, Germany, and Switzerland. All of them except the NFLGT project were successfully finalized during the resource allocation period. The NFLGT project team informed us that they decided not to use the provided resources. All projects were presented during the EOSC Regional Event in Budapest.

Project acronym	Principal investigator	Principal investigator country
TAVS-TAG	Blagoj Achevski	North Macedonia
DFTB-GPR	Dejan Kuneski	North Macedonia
MAGNANO	Yurii Chumakov	Moldova
FL4GLUE	Andreas Athenodorou	Cyprus
CoNTraSt	Veljko Jankovic	Serbia
ChFITrHM	Jaksa Vucicevic	Serbia
PLAIN	Srijit Paul	Germany
NFLGT	Javad Komijani	Switzerland

Table 9: List of accepted Computational physics projects, corresponding principal investigators, and their countries

4.4.1. TAVS-TAG

The TAVS-TAG project contributes to the exact assignment and interpretation of IRMPD spectroscopic data (infrared multiphoton dissociation) of gas-phase protonated glycine and betaine species tagged by molecular hydrogen and helium (Figure 8). The current calculations in the literature are based only on harmonic approximation using a scaling factor to adjust theoretically obtained values to the experimental data. Harmonic approximation may be appropriate for some vibrational modes, but certainly not for all. It is necessary to include anharmonic calculations, especially for X-H valence vibrations. So, the TAVS-TAG project aims to develop and implement exact and robust computational approaches to predict the anharmonic vibrational frequencies and the relevant frequency shifts upon tagging the above-mentioned species.

Figure 8: The located minima on the B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ PES of protonated betaine(+) tagged with a H₂ molecule from the O-H oscillator side (a) and from the hydrophobic side (b)

The advances in the gas phase vibrational spectroscopy of mass-selected ions, Cold Ion IR spectroscopy, especially infrared multiple photon dissociation (IRMPD) provides fundamental information for the characterization and understanding of the chemical state, the structure and dynamics of gas-phase biomolecules. An additional tool for suitable and exact interpretation and band assignment of an experimental spectrum is the theoretical approaches through available quantum mechanical computational codes, based on algorithms involving the double-harmonic normal mode approximation, and these are being often used in conjunction with a density functional theory (DFT) based method. The obtained experimental spectra of glycine and its protonated analog and the attempts for their suitable interpretation and band assignment are of great interest to many scientific areas. Therefore, the TAVS-TAG project aims to contribute to the assignment and exact interpretation of glycine spectra obtained by sophisticated experiments implementing their own computational protocols.

The conclusions reached so far strongly suggest that the good agreement between theoretical data based on double harmonic approximation and the experiments is often due to the cancellation of errors. However, if the exact fully anharmonic description of the relevant oscillators is implemented, in conjunction with an appropriately parametrized DFT combination of exchange and correlation functionals, physically justified excellent agreement with the experiment is achieved, shedding new light on the mechanisms governing the overall frequency shift, and provides additional insights into the very nature of these noncovalent interactions.

Avitohol cluster and FINKI cloud services allocated resources to support the TAVS-TAG project. In total, 50,000 CPU-core hours were allocated at the Avitohol and additional 16 VM cores at the FINKI. Also, the TAVS-TAG team was fully supported during the usage of the Schrödinger API thematic service for the calculation of the anharmonic vibrational frequencies of the species relevant to the project and on the basis of calculated X-H stretching vibrational potentials. No particular problems have been encountered in the course of project realization. Numerical simulations are performed using in-house written Fortran codes and codes written in the Mathematica application. Most of the planned calculations have been finalized, and a regular scientific paper is being prepared for submission. The TAVS-TAG team finalized the project by the end of January 2023.

4.4.2. DFTB-GPR

The main aim of the DFTB-GPR project was to perform reparameterization of the short-range repulsive potentials in DFTB calculations to further use them in simulations of

pharmaceutically relevant molecular crystals. For this purpose, the project team uses the Gaussian Process Regression approach. The reference values are computed with DFT, at a series of many geometries sampled from classical Monte Carlo or molecular dynamics simulations.

The advent of density functional theory (DFT) – based methods has revolutionized the theoretical chemistry and physics community. DFT enabled us to significantly extend the size range of the studied molecular systems with exact quantum theoretical approaches. Yet another breakthrough in the field has been enabled with the development of the density functional tight binding (DFTB) approximation to DFT. While the Harris-Foulkes energy expression in DFTB becomes identical to the more common Kohn-Sham formula if one sets ρ as the ground state density (ρ_{GS}), in the case when an approximate reference density is used ($\rho_0 \approx \rho_{GS}$), the two formalisms are different. The repulsive part of the DFTB potential is still empirical. Such a scheme (known as the DFTB0 in the current parlance) has shown great success for most of the covalently bonded systems. In polar or partially ionic systems, on the other hand, the approximation completely breaks down. This is due to the fact that, in the later systems, it is not possible to construct ρ_0 from isolated neutral atomic densities. To overcome this deficiency, the self-consistent charge (SCC) approach has been introduced, which includes the density fluctuations effects ($\delta\rho$) to the second or third order – the two approaches are nowadays known under the acronyms DFTB2 and DFTB3. It is, therefore, much more convenient to approximate E_{rep} with short-range atom pairwise contributions. Within the GPR framework, V_{rep} can be modelled as a linear combination of kernel (covariance) functions. V_{rep} is fitted so that the differences between the DFTB model (repulsion-less one) and DFT energies and forces (appropriately normalized) are minimized.

The conclusions reached so far strongly suggest that in order to achieve good agreement between theory and experimental structural and spectroscopic data for complex pharmaceutical crystals, one needs rather well-parametrized short-range repulsive potentials for the DFTB approach. Figure 9 shows a finite-cluster representation of the crystal structure of the pharmaceutically active substance clopidogrel hydrogensulfate (polymorphic form I). The structure of this cluster has been optimized by one of our developed methods.

Figure 9: A finite-cluster representation of the crystal structure of the pharmaceutically active substance clopidogrel hydrogensulfate (polymorphic form I)

For the DFTB-GPR project, the NI4OS-Europe project allocated 50,000 CPU-core hours at the Avitohol cluster and 16 VM-core at the FINKI Cloud, as well as access to the Gaussian API thematic service. Access to all these resources was provided during July 2023, and no particular problems have been encountered in the course of project realization. Most of the planned calculations have been finalized, and a regular scientific paper is being prepared for submission by the DFTB-GPR team. While completion of the project by the end of January 2023 may not be fully realized, the project team expects to do it soon afterward.

The future plans of the DFTB-GPR project team involve the implementation of developed methodologies on a series of other systems and their further improvement.

4.4.3. MAGNANO

The MAGNANO project was focused on the exploratory synthesis and characterization of new magnetic molecular materials by interlinking the smaller homo- and heterometallic clusters of 3d and 3d-4f ions or any their appropriate combinations into nano-sized aggregates using adequate linkers as carboxylate, O,N-based ligands, Schiff-base derivatives. Also, the project probed and modeled the physical (electronic and magnetic) properties of discrete coordination nano-clusters, looking for unusual magnetic behavior.

Nano-sized magnetic clusters have great potential for technological and industrial applications, especially in emerging fields such as the development of “intelligent” multifunctional materials, including magnetic sensors and future spintronic devices. The emerging area of molecular spintronics is seen as a foundation for information technology as it promises logic devices requiring significantly less operational energy than conventional semiconductor microelectronics. Magnetic clusters (MC) show fascinating magnetic phenomena such as single-molecule magnet behavior (SMM), macroscopic quantum tunnelling of magnetization, quantum phase interface, quantum coherence – key properties needed for materials to function as quantum bits (qubits), as well as have relevance to some fundamental physics such as high temperature superconductivity and colossal magnetoresistance. However, MC continues to be an “incomprehensible planet”; quite a lot of efforts still remain to focus on developing and understanding the complicated magnetic properties of nano-cluster magnets. In the Institute of Applied Physics, Chisinau, Moldova, the group of Assoc. Prof. S. Baca is concentrated on the study of 3d, 4f, and 3d-4f metal cations with carboxylates and additional N,O-containing co-ligands for development of magnetic nano-clusters. Dr. S. Baca developed new synthesis strategies based on archetypal geometrically frustrated triangular $\{\text{Fe}_3(\mu_3\text{-O})\}$ motifs that are interlinked via oxo, hydroxo, ethoxo, and carboxylate groups for highly condensed $\{\text{Fe}_7\}$, $\{\text{Fe}_8\}$, $\{\text{Fe}_{11}\}$, $\{\text{Fe}_{14}\}$, and $\{\text{Fe}_{16}\}$ nano-clusters. This group provides proof-of-concept for the successful creation of polynuclear $\{\text{Fe}_{18}\text{Ln}_6\}$, $\{\text{Mn}_{26}\text{Ln}_6\}$ single-molecule magnets. As a part of the MAGNANO project, several new design strategies are used and developed to ensure that efficient magnetic coupling is manifest in magnetic clusters. Advances in this field require a deep understanding of the electronic structure of magnets, and computational approaches play a key role in the understanding of magnetic properties. The theoretical and experimental studies of magnetic nanoclusters are directed toward designing novel molecular magnets with desired properties and performance.

The MAGNANO project team obtained access to the AVITOHOL cluster at the end of August 2022, where the three accounts have been created. AVITOHOL team provided full access

to all computational facilities of the cluster as well as to a fast-run queue for instant job execution. The Siesta and Atom software was installed on the cluster to study the electronic structure of magnetic nanoclusters. Till January 2022, The project team studied the magnetic interactions in the following single molecular magnets: $\{\text{Mn}_2\text{La}_2, \text{La}=\text{Gd}, \text{Tb}, \text{Dy}\}$, $\{\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}_6\text{Mn}^{\text{IV}}\text{Dy}^{\text{III}}_2\}$, $\{\text{Mn}_{26}\text{Ln}_6, \text{Ln}=\text{Dy}, \text{Tb}\}$ illustrated in Figure 10.

The project's team obtained access to the AVITOHOL cluster at the end of August 2021, so they spent only some dedicated CPU-core hours. Therefore, the team asked for a prolongation of calculations on the AVITOHOL cluster in order to study very effective SMMs as $\{\text{Mn}_{26}\text{Dy}_6\}$ and another 6-, 9-, 12-magnetic cores nanoclusters. Finally, the team prepared the paper (Nonanuclear pivalate cluster with a $\{\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}_6\text{Mn}^{\text{IV}}\text{Dy}^{\text{III}}_2\}$ core based on cubane subunits') for publication and orally presented some results at the Regional EOSC conference in Budapest (September 2021).

Figure 10: View of giant $\{\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}_6\text{Mn}^{\text{IV}}\text{Dy}^{\text{III}}_2\}$ and $\{\text{Mn}_{26}\text{Dy}_6\}$ nanosized clusters

4.4.4. FL4GLUE

The aim of the FL4GLUE project is the calculation of the spectrum of glueballs in Lattice QCD with four light dynamical quarks using maximally Twisted Mass Fermions (Figure 11). In addition, the project team wanted to perform a comparison of the extracted spectrum to the spectrum obtained in pure gauge SU(3) theory. The reason why they performed this study was to investigate the effect of light quarks on the spectrum of the hypothetical particles called glueballs. They perform this work with 4 light twisted mass fermions quarks mainly due to the fact that the number of configurations in such ensembles that is accessible is large of the order of O(20k) configurations. This enables the project team to extract the spectrum of glueballs with quite a good accuracy and to result in a meaningful comparison.

The project is performed within the framework of Lattice Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD). Lattice QCD is a well-established non-perturbative approach to solving the quantum chromodynamics (QCD) theory of quarks and gluons. It is a lattice gauge theory formulated on a four-dimensional grid or points in space and time. When the size of the lattice is taken infinitely large and its sites infinitesimally close to each other, the continuum QCD is recovered. Calculations in Lattice QCD require the usage of a vast number of computational resources. As a matter of fact, the computational intensity of such calculations has been driving the evolution of HPCs.

Figure 11: The spectrum of glueballs for the representations A_1^{++} , E^{++} , T_2^{++} , A_1^{-+} of the cubic group of rotations for the 4 flavor ensembles cB4.06.16 (left panel), cB4.06.24 (middle panel) and cC4.05.24 (right panel). The states of QCD with four flavors are denoted in purple while the states of pure gauge SU(3) in green. The masses are presented in dimensionless units where t_0 is a scale called the Wilson flow time

The FL4GLUE project was granted 100,000 CPU-core hours at the ISABELA HPC installation. In the beginning, the project team faced a number of difficulties in accessing the accounts, but this was immediately resolved through the helpdesk in collaboration with the ISABELA team. Most of the tasks related to the initial plan of the project have been accomplished. What is now missing is the calculation of the energies of di-torelon states in the spectrum of glueballs. However, the initial plan of the project has been finalized, and this has led to a presentation at the annual Lattice Gauge Theories meeting of 2022 [10] and, subsequently, to a publication of proceedings in Open Access. The project team is currently in the process of writing a longer article [11] which will be submitted to an open-access journal. All the data produced within the project will be openly published in Zenodo.

4.4.5. CoNTraSt

The main aim of the CoNTraSt project is to examine charge transport in the one-dimensional Holstein model using numerically exact quantum dynamics methods that are formulated directly in real time.

The Holstein model is the simplest model describing how the interaction of an electron with quantum lattice vibrations brings about the formation of the polaron quasiparticle. Polaron transport properties are regarded as highly relevant to the electronic properties of many widely studied systems, such as organic semiconductors, photosynthetic pigment-protein complexes, transition-metal oxides, etc. Approximate methods to compute polaron mobility are numerically expedient and physically transparent, but rely on assumptions whose domain of validity is often unknown. On the other hand, numerically exact methods do not rely on any additional assumptions (apart from those contained in the model Hamiltonian), but require intensive computations.

Within the CoNTraSt project, the team relies on the synergy between two numerically exact methods formulated in real time: the real-time quantum Monte Carlo (QMC) and hierarchical equations of motion (HEOM) method. QMC scales favorably with the chain length N , but provides results for time-dependent current–current correlation function up to relatively short times due to its dynamical sign problem. The HEOM method becomes intractable for large N , it has an additional control parameter (the maximum hierarchy depth D) with respect to which convergence should be checked, but provides the current–current correlation function up to very long real times, which is of paramount importance to reliably predict mobility. In each parameter regime, we perform QMC simulations for different N to find the necessary chain length. Equipped with this result, the CoNTraSt project team performs short-time HEOM computations for different D to find the necessary maximum hierarchy depth. With both N and D at hand, they propagate HEOM up to long real times and extract the mobility. The main result, the temperature-dependent mobility in different parameter regimes, is given in Figure 12 (a)–(c). We note that a couple of thousand CPU-hours is invested into obtaining each point in Figure 12 (a)–(c).

In the following month (till January 31, 2023), the CoNTraSt project team plans to more closely inspect the anti-adiabatic regime (Figure 12 (c)), where they encountered numerical problems and obtained preliminary results only in a small number of temperature points. Also, numerical instabilities prevented the team from obtaining results at high temperatures in Figure 12 (a) and at low temperatures in Figure 12 (b). In the following month, the CoNTraSt team plans to study these regimes in the so-called bubble approximation. It decouples the two-particle current–current correlation function into a product of two single-particle quantities, the computation of which is relatively cheap and not plagued by numerical instabilities.

Figure 12: Temperature (T) dependence of the direct-current charge carrier mobility μ_{dc} in the one-dimensional Holstein model in (a) the adiabatic regime $\hbar\omega_0/J = 1/3$, (b) the extreme quantum regime $\hbar\omega_0/J = 1$, and (c) the anti-adiabatic regime $\hbar\omega_0/J = 3$ for different electron–phonon interaction strengths. The parameters of the model are the phonon frequency ω_0 , the electronic coupling J , and the electron–phonon interaction strength G . \hbar is the reduced Planck constant, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, e_0 is the elementary charge, while a_t is the lattice constant. Dashed lines serve as guides to the eye

The CoNTraSt project is assigned 300,000 CPU-hours on the ARIS supercomputing facility, together with 1 TB of storage. By December 26, 2022, they have used around 2/3 of the assigned CPU time. The project team has not encountered any technical or other issues while using resources. We expect that the results we obtained in the course of the project will result in at least one research paper.

In the future, the project team plans to use similar methodologies to study more complicated models with the electron–phonon interaction, such as the Peierls or Su–Schrieffer–Heeger model. Their ambitious plans require extensive use of HPC resources, and they are happy to participate in some new open calls for CPU time on the facilities available in our region.

4.4.6. ChFITrHM

The ChFITrHM project team has investigated the hydrodynamic properties of the square lattice Hubbard model. A recent experiment aimed at simulating the Hubbard model with ultracold atoms in an optical lattice suggested that a particular hydrodynamic theory governs the charge fluctuations at long wavelengths [12]. This hydrodynamic model has only two parameters, namely the diffusion constant, D , and the momentum relaxation rate, Γ . The team obtained results that give support to the hydrodynamic hypothesis.

First, the ChFITrHM team has worked out analytically the asymptotic high-frequency behavior of the charge fluctuation spectrum. Applying this knowledge to the weakly coupled Hubbard model, we can conclude that, if the hydrodynamic hypothesis is correct, the product of the two hydrodynamic parameters, $D\Gamma$, must tend to a constant equal $2t^2$, where t is the hopping amplitude. The equation of motion for the current can be derived exactly for the Hubbard model, in general. Comparing it to the constituent equation of the proposed phenomenological hydrodynamic theory, one sees similar asymptotic behavior of $D\Gamma$, but additional terms make it impossible to make a rigorous connection between the hydrodynamic and microscopic parameters of the Hubbard model.

The numerical calculations support the high-temperature limit result for the product $D\Gamma$. Assuming the validity of the hydrodynamic theory, the team can extract from the optical conductivity the values of D and Γ separately. They find that, up to a multiplicative constant, the temperature dependence of the two parameters varies little with the increasing coupling. The results are presented in Figure 13. The strong coupling asymptotic behavior of $D\Gamma$ seems to coincide with the high-temperature asymptotic behavior.

The ChFITrHM team has also computed resistivity in a big part of the phase diagram. The results coincide qualitatively with the Boltzmann semi-classical theory [13], but there are strong quantitative differences. The team also connected the observation of linear-in-temperature resistivity at half-filling with the quantum critical line that was recently observed to pass through the half-filled point at zero temperature [14].

Figure 13: Results for the effective hydrodynamic parameters in the Hubbard model as a function of temperature and as a function of coupling constant. At weak coupling, the Kubo bubble calculation simplifies. At moderate coupling, we compute the full Kubo bubble. At strong coupling, the ChFITrHM project employs the finite temperature Lanczos method (data provided by Jure Kokalj and Martin Ulaga)

4.4.7. PLAIN

The PLAIN project aims to investigate the phase structure of the 3D Ising Model, 4D Ising Model, and simple Gauge Theory models such as compact 3D Z(2) and 3D U(1) Gauge Theories using machine learning techniques. Namely, the project team constructed a deep-learning autoencoder network and used it to identify the critical temperature in the aforementioned systems. In addition, the team investigated how the latent variable is connected to the order parameter of each system and whether there is a configuration of the neural network which can reproduce the right physics of the system, including the right critical exponents (Figure 14). The application of machine learning techniques in statistical systems has bloomed during the last four years, with the investigation of phase structure being one of the most interesting topics. The aforementioned systems have not been investigated using unsupervised machine learning, and thus, this is a timely project.

The phase structure of discrete spin systems and simple gauge theories provide the best testing grounds to study the efficacy of deep-learning autoencoders. Investigating the 3D Ising near criticality provides a plethora of information about the conjectured QCD critical point and the QCD Phase diagram around it because they belong to the same static universality class. Deep Learning Autoencoders equip a lattice practitioner with a novel data-driven framework to quantify the order parameter and critical properties of their lattice simulations of physical systems.

Figure 14: The Latent variable as a function of temperature for the 3D Ising model and four different box volumes. Clearly the two states which correspond to the two orientations of spins collapse at the critical temperature noted by the red line. This enables us to extract the critical temperature using the latent variable as a pseudo-order parameter

The PLAIN project was granted 10,000 CPU-core and 10,000 GPU-card hours at the ARIS HPC installation. The project team reported problems related to the ARIS access, and these were solved via the helpdesk. The team used allocated resources to investigate the phase structure of the 2D Ising, 3D Ising, and 4D Ising models, and now they are moving to 3D Z(2) gauge theory. The PLAIN team reported all achievements up to January 2023, but not all of the initially planned goals have been achieved. The project team still has to investigate the phase structure of Z(2) and other Z(N) theories, as well as lattice QCD systems.

4.5. Other scientific domain projects

We received only one project outside the four flagship scientific fields in the open call. The SANDPAPER project analyzes and optimizes the performances of edge resource migration in a highly dynamic environment with frequently changing user requirements. The principal investigator of this project is Katja Gilly from Miguel Hernández University, Spain. The project is successfully finalized in the allocation period, and in this section, we present the main results and outcomes.

4.5.1. SANDPAPER

SANDPAPER project is focused on the research of adaptive edge computing solutions by exploring the tools and technologies that are nowadays available both for simulating and deploying edge computing systems. The main goal of SANDPAPER was to analyze and optimize the performances of edge resource migration in a highly dynamic environment with frequently changing user requirements by researching the optimal decisions on when

and where to migrate edge services relative to the user location and available system monitoring information in order to guarantee minimum latency.

The ICIPRO Cloud service allocated resources required by the SANDPAPER project. During July 2022, access was provided to 6 VMs, which technical characteristics are given in Table 10. Using these resources, the project team implemented their edge simulation workflow illustrated in Figure 15. The team set up the environment, performed edge computing simulations, and obtained a new set of results with a new Cloudsim library of 5G-related protocols implementation. The results were analyzed and compared with results produced by other 5G libraries used for previous simulation experiments.

Hostname	CPU-cores	RAM (GB)	Disk space (GB)	Local IP address
srv01	16	32	3,572	10.0.0.2
srv02	8	8	100	10.0.0.3
srv03	4	4	40	10.0.0.4
srv04	8	16	100	10.0.0.5
srv05	8	16	100	10.0.0.6
srv06	8	8	100	10.0.0.7

Table 10: Technical characteristics of the provided VMs at the ICIPRO Cloud service

On the other hand, an experimental scenario has been configured in several VMs implementing an OSM Mano environment based on a Kubernetes cluster as the virtualized infrastructure. The project team collected performance information of deployed containers as network functions, as well as their migration from one worker node to another. Currently, the team is working on defining and implementing the proactive approaches to be applied to the obtained datasets.

The SANDPAPER project team found some problems during the execution of the simulations, as the batch processes were stopped when the online connection was broken, even though the jobs were launched as background tasks. They managed to amend this problem by repeating by hand each group of simulations. Also, they have been faced with some incompatibility problems as the OS installed was Ubuntu 22.04 instead of Ubuntu 20.04. Once the problem was detected, the ICIPRO technical team provided a solution within the minimum slot of time.

Since the ICIPRO Cloud service is implemented on an Azure Cloud, graphical access to non-Windows OS platforms is difficult, especially practically impossible from Linux distributions such as Ubuntu. On the other hand, the service can be accessed through the terminal interface. Enabling access to the graphical console for all OS platforms is a suggestion for improvement by the SANDPAPER team.

Figure 15: ETSI’s Multi-access Edge Computing application instantiation process flowchart

The SANDPAPER project team published a paper related to the experimental work they have been reproducing on NI4OS-Europe provided resources [15]. The results obtained using the NI4OS-Europe resources they are planning to present at the upcoming 29th Annual International Conference On Mobile Computing And Networking, MobiCom'23 [16].

5. Conclusions

The NI4OS-Europe open call for proposals for projects using services provided via the NI4OS-Europe catalogue is proof of the EOSC concept applied at the regional but also pan-European scale. Throughout the call, the researchers from various fields tested all details of the intricate EOSC environment, verifying seamless access, FAIR management, and reliable reusability of research data. The complex architecture of the NI4OS-Europe hidden behind the catalogue offers European researchers an environment where they can develop, publish, find and re-use data, tools, and services for research, innovation, and educational purposes.

During the call, we offered all on-boarded resources and services registered within the catalogue. These were fully equipped with user manuals and related policies, incorporated into the NI4OS-Europe pre-production environment, and previously tested and evaluated by researchers from Life Science, Climate Science, Digital Cultural Heritage, and Computational Physics communities [3]. Due to the high demand for generic services (HPC and Cloud services), whose utilization is effectively 100%, we performed allocation of these resources taking care to ensure their seamless use by the open call projects. In collaboration with the resource providers, we allocated 6.2 million CPU-core hours, 402,000 GPU-card hours, 10,000 Xeon Phi-card hours, 364 VM cores, and a significant amount of storage space.

The access mode of the regional computing-intensive services is typically peer-reviewed or excellence-based. Therefore, all received proposals underwent a technical and scientific review to determine the eligibility and suitability of applications for the requested services. The criteria for the evaluation of projects for accessing the available resources were defined [3] and published as a part of the call. In total, we have received 21 proposals, while 20 of them were granted access to the NI4OS-Europe services. The focus of the call was on Life Sciences, Climatology, Digital Cultural Heritage and Computational Physics scientific communities, and we approved access to 5, 2, 4, and 8 projects from these areas, respectively. An additional accepted project was from the edge computing research field.

Following the results of the evaluation, we distributed the accepted projects over previously allocated resources. All projects requested at least one type of generic service: 16 projects requested HPC resources, 5 Cloud resources, and two asked for storage resources at the Archival service. In addition, six projects requested access to thematic services and three needed access to the NI4OS-Europe repository service. In total, all projects were granted 3.17 million CPU-core hours, 115,000 GPU-card hours, 166 VM cores, and 49 TBs of storage space.

The computational services were granted to the awarded proposals over the period of 7 months, from July 2022 to January 2023, and for data services the allocation period was extended until March 2023. During this time, principal investigators received full technical support via the project helpdesk. We note that we did not receive any objections regarding the provided support. As a result, 16 out of 20 projects were successfully finalized during the allocation period, while four did not use or only partially used the allocated resources. All projects were presented during the EOSC Regional Event in Budapest. We stress that 5 of them had already published their results in articles in peer-reviewed journals, while the other projects are still working on the manuscripts.